

Re-assessment of structural properties of heat treatment on the NiTi alloy

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Scientists are interested in the structural characteristics of materials having solid state effects-based phase transition properties as well as the linkage between phase transition kinetics and structural phase transformation. In this study, the impact of heat treatment on the structural characteristics at room temperature was attempted to be investigated beginning with the manufacture of NiTi material in volumetric form. These research' observations of the phase transition at almost room temperature and structural instability serve as its foundation. The annealing process causes a reevaluation of NiTi alloys. As a result of the heat treatment, the high temperature phase (Austenite, B2) and the low temperature phase (Martensite, B19') coexist, despite the fact that the crystalline structure of the high temperature phase is present near ambient temperature before manufacturing. In this instance, it is undeniably demonstrated that the phase transformation temperature can be changed with heat treatment, and in light of these results, this study can reserve as a model for other situations.

1. Introduction

Today's increased global warming makes it all the more important to find technological cooling alternatives. In contrast, cooling systems are now widely implemented. Among the many applications of cooling technology are the maintenance of electronic gadgets, the preservation of perishable food supplies, and the facilitation of ventilation systems. Traditional methods of cooling rely on gas compression systems as their primary mechanism of operation. Greenhouse emissions and the usage of hazardous liquids are both exacerbated by the gases used in cooling systems. Consequently, it is important to study and create new methods of cooling that don't rely on the use of potentially dangerous chemicals that are chemicals that are environmentally friendly and inexpensive. Low efficiency is one of the most fundamental issues with traditional cooling systems. There is a need for the development of efficient replacement cooling methods for these already in-use are inefficient systems. Scientists thought this could be done with "solid-state" cooling, which is made possible by the caloric effects of magnetocaloric, electrocaloric, and superelastic effects.

In the 1930s, the first experiments with the superelastic effect were conducted on the shape memory alloys Au-Cd and Cu-Zn. However, since its

discovery in 1963, Ni-Ti has been the most popular and studied shape memory and superelastic alloy. These alloys were created and analyzed throughout the subsequent years. Doped Ni-Ti alloys with elements like copper, chromium, palladium, and platinum have been developed, as have doped Cu-based alloys with elements including aluminum, nickel, zinc, manganese, and iron. In the early 19th century, Moya et al. [2] recorded temperature variations of 0.2 K due to elastic heat in some metals and dry woods. Superelastic latent heat and temperature fluctuations were originally studied in the 1980s [3-6], but only in Ni-Ti and Cu-based alloys. These investigations are physically connected to thermal modifications enacted throughout structure transformations and for cooling or heat pumping functions [7]. The elastocaloric effect was first detected in 1992 by Nittekin et al. as a negative adiabatic temperature change in the Fe-Rh alloy at temperatures close to room temperature (under 529 MPa stress at 305 K). Bonnot et al. (2008) used adiabatic temperature variations in Cu-Zn-Al alloy to evaluate the elastocaloric effect, finding that a mechanical stress of 28.5 MPa results in a temperature shift of 15 K near ambient temperature. A negative adiabatic temperature value of -6 K was recorded between

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200 K and 350 K [9-10] when the applied tension was increased by Vives et al. The temperature of polycrystalline Ni-Ti wires rose to 25.5 K when a tension of 650 MPa was applied to them. The adiabatic temperature decrease was measured to be -17 K [11].

Using elastocaloric analysis, Osmer et al. [12, 13] determined that the Ni-Ti thin film experienced both a positive adiabatic temperature change of 17 K and a negative adiabatic temperature change of 16 K. By stabilizing the elastocaloric characteristics, Bechtold et al. found that the Ni-Ti-Cu alloy exhibited greater superelastic behavior and, hence, better fatigue life than an undoped sample. Doping enhances structural change, and the resulting temperatures are well above ambient [14]. In 2013, Xiao et al. reported that an elastocaloric effect may be seen in a single crystal Fe-Pd alloy undergoing continuous structural change, and that the alloy's superelastic behavior displays nearly 0% hysteresis. This hysteresis's seemingly little value can be a significant benefit, but the costs cannot be recovered. The elastocaloric impact is about 2 K restricted between 240 K and 280 K [15]. Natural rubber's elastocaloric action was investigated by Guyomer et al. and the sample is a polymer of shape memory alloys, and it has been reported that at 297 K, the sample stretches by around 70% [16]. Despite the elastocaloric effect's promise as a cooling device, it still has some serious flaws. Even so, data from the US Department of the Interior in 2014 shows that non-vapor compression HVAC technologies other than vapor compression refrigeration have the most promising future [17].

In this study, it is revisited the Ni-Ti alloy in-situ high cooling rate via structural properties whether phase transition properties in cooling technology, which promise efficient and environmentally friendly energy that will not cause carbon monoxide, harmful gases and greenhouse effect, can be an alternative to traditional vapor compression systems. In order to reach this conclusion, the alloy was produced on a laboratory scale based on NiTi alloys, which is one of the best known super-elastic materials. Afterwards, its structural properties were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscope (SEM), and stress property of annealed sample is examined by the mechanical measuring device in the vicinity of room temperature.

2. Results and Discussion

SEM microscope images of NiTi before and after heat treatment are seen in Fig.1. It is well-known that SE and BSD detectors are widely utilized in SEM. These not only facilitate surface analysis, but also reveal variations in composition analyses due

to phase differences at the surface. Since the sample under study is dominated by a single shade of gray, we can conclude that it lacks any accumulating or compositional differences. Elemental mapping of images of NiTi after heat treatment is depicted in Fig. 1e. The image labels the states of Ni and Ti atoms by number, and each green and red dot corresponds to one of those states. As a result, no buildup or non-homogeneous situation was observed. According to energy dispersive X-ray (EDX), Ni 51.1 (± 1.1) % and Ti 48.9 (± 0.4) % for alloy was found to be the average estimated compositions. The computed difference is expected to be close to the values of the margin of error. Energy-dispersed X-ray pictures further revealed that the structure did not contain any observable stages of change. No compositional heterogeneity has been found, and the reported compositions are the average of various locations on the surfaces of the alloys.

Figure 1. SEM microscope images (Secondary electron detector, SED and back-scattering electron detector, BSD) of NiTi alloy before heat treatment (a,c) and after heat treatment (b,d), elemental mapping of NiTi (e) and EDX spectrum of elemental mapping (f)

Figure 2 displays X-ray diffraction patterns at room temperature for both heat-treated and untreated samples. Existing crystal structures are graphed with their Bragg positions (B2 and B19 structures) labeled according to their phases, and the positions of their atoms in the unit cell are explicitly listed. To investigate the effect of annealing on structural properties of these alloys,

Figure 2. a) XRD patterns of as-cast (thermal untreated) and heat-treated samples, inset of B19 (Orthorhombic as donated ¶) and B2 (Cubic as donated §) schematic of crystal structures, b), c) and d) W-H curves of phases of untreated and treated samples.

the XRD analysis reveals that the annealed NiTi is almost entirely Martensitic, whereas the Austenite phase is predominated in the unannealed sample. As a result, observing the structural phase transition for these types of alloys requires the annealing process. Micro-strain and domain size in as-cast and annealed NiTi can be determined using the Williamson-Hall method. It is predicated on the idea that the approximate equations for size broadening, denoted by β_L , and strain broadening, denoted by β_e , change considerably differently with regard to the Bragg angle, denoted by:

$$\beta_L = \frac{K\lambda}{L \cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_e = C\epsilon \tan\theta \quad (2)$$

Williamson and Hall's approach to simplifying the problem is to assume that the convolution is either a simple sum or a sum of squares. Putting the first of them into practice,

$$\beta_{tot} = \beta_e + \beta_L = C\epsilon \tan\theta + \frac{K\lambda}{L \cos\theta} \quad (3)$$

We can get the strain component ($C\epsilon$) and the size component ($K\lambda/L$) by graphing total $\beta_{tot}\cos\theta$ against $\sin\theta$. In this situation in Fig. 2 b, c and d, the Williamson-Hall plot displayed a positive slope, ruling out the possibility of employing this technique [18]. The crystalline sizes and microstrain values B2 and B19 phases untreated and treated samples are 46 nm, 22nm and 23 nm, and 2.53×10^{-3} , 1.54×10^{-4} and 1.66×10^{-3} , respectively.

Many reserachers and studies have proven the connection between solid-state cooling and structural. Different production strategies have been tried out, beginning with the bulk synthesis of

these materials. The near-room-temperature phase transition and structural instabilities serve as the basis for these investigations.

It was observed that the superelastic properties of the alloy emerged after the heat treatment, and a 4.7 % stressing occurred on the Ni-Ti alloy when the force was applied on it at room temperature. This can be seen from the stress-strain curve that was obtained in Fig.3, and it can be seen that the superelastic properties of the alloy emerged after the heat treatment. In keeping with the fact that Ni-Ti superelastic alloys have the ability to remember their previous shapes, it has been discovered that this transformation can be undone and that the process may be repeated. The obtained strain and stress magnitudes from comparable investigations differ [19,20]. The current authors of general consensus is that it would be appropriate to explain the difference's origins, for instance, by referring to previous circumstances it faced during manufacture. As a result, it has come to light that the created superelastic alloy possesses features that are suited for use in elastocaloric coolers.

Figure 3. Stress-strain curve of heat-treated alloy.

3. Conclusion

The goal of this research was to determine the properties of NiTi alloy with structural properties if super-elastic cooling systems, which promise efficient and environmentally friendly energy without increasing carbon emissions, causing harmful gases, or contributing to the greenhouse effect, can be used as a replacement for conventional vapor compression systems. One of the most well-known super-elastic materials, NiTi alloys served as the basis for this alloy's small-scale production in a laboratory setting. Using an X-ray diffraction equipment and scanning electron microscope, it was determined that the alloy formed at room temperature in the B19 orthorhombic structure of the martensite phase, the low temperature phase. The B2 cubic crystal structure was identified in the austenite phase after 120 minutes of heat treatment at 1023 K. This is the high temperature phase. Inspecting the alloy with a scanning electron microscope revealed that its structure was uniform before and after the heat treatment, and that there was no discernible change in its chemical make-up.

The thermal treatment of the NiTi alloy has yielded the following results in this work:

- as predicted, the appropriate thermal treatment is applied, and the overall NiTi structure is maintained in the homogeneous state under investigation,

- the low temperature phase content appears to be decreasing with increased thermal treatment,

- As-cast, non-heated samples do not exhibit first order at ambient temperature, although thermal treatment is apparent;

To fully understand these effects, according to the authors, more heat treatment, thermal measurement, and magnetic studies is required.

Method

The required elemental purity for the alloys was accomplished by the purchasing of commercial impurities Ni (98%) and Ti (98%). In order to purify these materials used in industrial applications, they were subjected to a five-time times arc melting process in order to remove high amounts of materials such as carbon and oxygen from the main composition before alloying. Doping amounts in the alloys were determined by weighing the individual elements using a precise electronic balance (0.01 mg) and referencing their mole ratios. Alloy-forming components were put in a water-cooled copper crucible before being sucked to a pressure of 10^{-3} mbar using a mechanical pump in the arc

melting process. After the system was evacuated to the desired level, an arc was created by connecting the crucible to the arc's tip and running current through it. The substance is melted by passing the arc tip over the individual elements that make it up. Each component was melted in its own furnace during the initial phase of the melting process. A Ni_{51.1}Ti_{48.9} alloy was then melted together to create an instance. To ensure that the compositional distributions of the bulk alloys were consistent, the melting procedure was performed 5 times, with the material being flipped upside down between each iteration.

In order to ensure the homogeneity of the alloys and to eliminate the hardness that may remain in the alloy, heat treatment was applied to all alloys at 1023 K temperature for 120 minutes after being imprisoned in the quartz tube. Then, in order to remove the scratches on the sample, the scratches were tried to be removed by using the sanding process. Scratches were removed using the sanding process for the scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

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Authors' contributions

M.Ç.: Formal Analysis, Validation, Writing-Original Draft; G.D.Y.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Original Draft, Writing-Review & Editing Supervision; E.Y.: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing-Original Draft, Project administration.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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